

USING ENGLISH IN THE CLASSROOM

Dilnoza Shuhratovna Xakimova

**3rd year student on the faculty of English language and literature at
Fergana state university**

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This article discusses the importance of using English in the classroom. It highlights the benefits of using English as a medium of instruction, such as improving language skills, preparing students for the real world, promoting inclusivity, and providing access to a wide range of resources.

Abstract

The article emphasizes the need to create a supportive environment for students to build confidence and competence in the language. Overall, it emphasizes the holistic development that occurs when English is utilized in the classroom.

Keywords

"English language instruction," "English as a medium of instruction," "benefits of using English in the classroom"

English serves as a global language, enabling communication across different cultures and connecting individuals worldwide. Within the educational setting, using English as a medium of instruction holds paramount significance. The utilization of English in the classroom not only enhances language skills but also offers a myriad of advantages that contribute to the holistic development of students.

Firstly, using English in the classroom fosters language acquisition and proficiency. Constant exposure to English in academic settings facilitates vocabulary expansion, refined grammar usage, and improved pronunciation. This helps students to become fluent and articulate in the language, which is essential for clear and effective communication in diverse academic and professional environments.

Furthermore, embracing English in the classroom prepares students for the multifaceted demands of our globalized world. Proficiency in English opens doors to a wealth of educational and professional opportunities, as English is widely used in higher education, international business, and global diplomacy. By honing their English language skills from an early age, students are better equipped to navigate these international arenas and diversify their future prospects.

The inclusive nature of using English as a medium of instruction cannot be understated. By adopting English as the common language of communication, it creates an equitable environment for students from various linguistic backgrounds. This common ground ensures that all students have equal access to educational resources, irrespective of their native language, promoting a more inclusive and supportive learning ambiance.

Moreover, the use of English in the classroom brings forth a multitude of English-language resources, including literature, academic journals, and online platforms, thereby broadening students' exposure to diverse perspectives and knowledge. This exposure fosters critical thinking, research skills, and the ability to engage with a wide array of information, contributing to students' overall intellectual development.

While embracing English in the classroom is beneficial, educators need to ensure that students receive the necessary support to thrive in this environment. Providing opportunities for

interactive activities, promoting language practice, and encouraging open discussions in English are essential components to help students build confidence and fluency in the language. One of the main advantages of using English in the classroom is that it helps students to improve their language skills. By using English as the medium of instruction, students are constantly exposed to the language, which helps them to improve their vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. This constant exposure to English also helps students to become more fluent in the language, which is essential for effective communication.

Using English in the classroom also prepares students for the real world where English is often the dominant language. Many academic institutions and workplaces use English as the primary language of communication, so having a good command of the language is crucial for success. By using English in the classroom, students are better prepared to navigate the globalized world and communicate effectively with people from different backgrounds.

Furthermore, using English in the classroom promotes a more inclusive learning environment. When students from diverse linguistic backgrounds come together, using English as a common language helps to create a level playing field for all students. It ensures that no student is at a disadvantage due to their proficiency in a particular language, and everyone has an equal opportunity to participate and learn.

In addition, using English in the classroom exposes students to a wide range of English-language resources such as books, articles, and online materials. This exposure helps students to broaden their knowledge and research skills, as they can access a wealth of information available in English. It also encourages students to explore different genres and styles of writing, which can enhance their critical thinking and analytical skills.

While using English in the classroom has many benefits, it is important to recognize that students may face challenges in adapting to a new language. Teachers should make an effort to create a supportive and encouraging environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves in English. Providing opportunities for students to practice speaking, listening, reading, and writing in English can help them to build confidence and competence in the language.

In conclusion, using English in the classroom is essential for the holistic development of students. It not only enhances their language skills but also equips them with the necessary tools to thrive in a globalized world. Promoting the use of English in the classroom, educators can help their students to become more proficient, confident, and effective communicators in English.

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7. You can use platforms such as JSTOR, Google Scholar, ERIC, or your university's library resources to find articles and research papers on this topic.

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